

VIT
NATIONAL CONFERENCE

Vidyalankar Institute of Technology

Wadala (E), Mumbai -400037

VIT
Vidyalankar
Institute of
Technology
www.vit.edu.in

**National Conference
on**

"Innovations in Electronics & Information Technology"

This is to certify that

Jayen Modi

Presented a paper on

**"Mathematical model for Car to move with Ideal velocity
using concepts of Adaptive Controllers"**

at the National Conference,

"Innovations in Electronics & Information Technology" organized by
Vidyalankar Institute of Technology, Wadala, Mumbai-37 on October 05-06, 2009.

Prof. Shrikant Velankar
Convener, IEIT 2009

Dr. Prashant Sonare
Principal, VIT